

THE EDUCATIONAL IMPORTANCE OF DANCE

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Abstract: dance art is an integral part of our national heritage. It reflects the traditions of the past, deep values. The more we study its basis, the more new aspects will be revealed and it will express how rich art is.

Key words: national dance, choreography, art, plastic movements, performance art, culture, tradition.

Reforms of historical significance are being implemented in our country, which serve to raise the national dance art of national and universal importance to a higher position. Our national dance is an example of art that reflects the history, spirit, hopes and dreams of the nation. Studying its history means studying and researching people's customs, traditions, present and future.

The fact that our people accept dance as their favorite form of art is due to the perfect and unique synthesis of music and body movement. The art of dance is close to the people's hearts with its unique content and deep meaning. Especially through folk dances, people's history, way of life, unique freshness typical of valleys, oases and countries, work process, high culture, human qualities, expressions of women and girls, strength and pride of boys and men, pride of children. People's sorrows and pains are described along with the celebration of their life, holidays and joys. In order to convey human life and events in nature to the people through the art of dance, it is necessary to ensure its imagery.

The most important thing in creating a choreographic image is to choose a movement that helps to show a particular character in the dance. The meaning of the movements of the body, legs, and hands should correspond to the content of the dance. Therefore, music is chosen with a specific goal in mind before staging each dance. Master ballet masters take into account the ability and ability of the dancer when choosing a dancer for solo parts of a solo dance or public dance. They carefully selected their characteristic melody and used appropriate movements.

The teachers asked the dancers to use their acting skills. They performed this dance with great skill, special enthusiasm, grace and grace, which left an indelible mark on the hearts of our people and formed the tradition that formed the foundation of the dance school today. How the art of dance developed in history, what caused it, we cannot provide clear evidence, we can only guess based on certain sources. However, in some cases, these assumptions may turn out to be wrong. The highest forms of dance, which are the products of professional dancers and musicians, are preserved and developed in the repertoire of professional dancers, as well as among dance amateurs who imitate professional dancers. This situation will serve as an important resource for artists who want to learn the art of dance in the future.

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